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Development of a Sensitivity Tool for Time-Domain Studies on Gamma-Ray Instruments HESS, CTAO and Fermi-LAT

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Abstract

Every telescope is limited by several factors in its ability to detect photons. How low the energy flux of a light source can be, to still be distinguishable from the respective background, is what defines the sensitivity of an observation instrument. Thus, testing methods to improve the sensitivity of telescopes can be useful. Besides shifting the detection requirements, like lowering the needed significance and the signal-background ratio, which increases the chance of observational misinterpretations, another option to enhance the sensitivity is to choose a longer observation time. In order to see how strong these effects are and how good certain gamma-ray light sources can be resolved by the two IACTs HESS and CTAO (in its 'Alpha Configuration'), as well as the space telescope Fermi-LAT, we developed a tool for these instruments, which is based on a `gammapy` and a `fermipy` code. After presenting its functionality, it's used to analyse the detection of typical gamma-ray source types at galactic and extragalactic distance. The tool was able to demonstrate the difference of 1 and 2 orders of magnitude for the sensitivities of the two types of gamma-ray instruments in various plots against energy like Figure 2.1, while Figure 2.3 shows the time-dependent improvement of the sensitivities. Further, it was apparent from the comparisons for different sets of criteria, that the higher detection uncertainties for looser requirements came with an improvement of the sensitivities by more than 200%. But the code was also used to illustrate how the calculated sensitivities compare to some detected gamma-ray events like the Nova RS Ophiuchi and the blazar PKS0736+01. Especially for the latter, it became clear how misleading the calculated sensitivity curves can be, since the observed flux went far below the sensitivities on a wide range of energy.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Gamma-ray Astronomy

1.1.1 Energy range

Gamma-ray astronomy, as the name says, is concerned with the observation of electromagnetic waves in the gamma-ray regime. Taking the definition by E. L. Chupp this energy regime starts at 100 keV and goes as high as 10^{21} eV (cf. [2] p.1). Thus, the range of gamma-ray energies covers the domain from below High Energy (HE), over Very High Energy (VHE) up to Ultra High Energy (UHE), where the respective regimes are defined like in [3] p. 210 (HE > 30 MeV, VHE > 100 GeV) and in [4] p. 161 (UHE in PeV regime). With the corresponding frequencies being even higher than X-rays, gamma-rays therefore represent the upper limit of the electromagnetic spectrum, which also means that their production corresponds to some of the highest energetic events of the universe.

Figure 1.1: The Electromagnetic Spectrum. Credit: NASA/CXC/SAO/MPE

1.1.2 Gamma-ray Production

Typical gamma-rays are of non-thermal nature, because for the necessary temperatures of around 10^{13} K the photons would be so dense, they would mostly collide and create e.g. electron-positron pairs (cf. [3] p.24). Murthy and Wolfendale summarize the dominant production processes of gamma-ray lines (the clear spectral lines in the gamma-ray regime) as "[...] (a) e+ e- annihilations, (b) neutron capture reactions, (c) the de-excitation of target nuclei struck by energetic protons and other particles, together with projectile nuclei excited by impact, or by virtue of the fact that they are the radioactive products of stellar ejecta, and (d) Landau transitions" ([5] p.1). More important for most observations though is the gamma-ray continuum. It is mostly caused by electrons, which besides annihilating with positrons and doing Inverse

Compton (IC) scattering, can emit Bremsstrahlung, synchrotron radiation as well as curvature radiation (cf. [5] p.5) in the considered energy regime. IC scattering is an interaction where ultra-relativistic electrons scatter of lower energetic photons, transferring a lot of that energy onto the photon. Bremsstrahlung is the process in which electrically charged particles are attracted or repelled by other nearby charges, making them send out radiation as a consequence of their deceleration. As for synchrotron and curvature radiation, both occur when relativistic charged particles move into a magnetic field, circulate and emit photons as a result. While for the former the magnetic field needs to be transversal to the particle direction, triggering the Lorentz force to provoke the spiral movement, for the latter the particles are forced to move aligned to a strong magnetic field, which itself is curved, leading to the circulation (for all these processes cf. [5] p.8 ff.). But also protons can contribute to gamma-ray emission, mostly through inelastic hadronic collisions, forming highly energetic neutral pions that can decay into gamma-rays (cf. [5] p.10).

1.1.3 Gamma-ray Sources

Events that represent candidates for gamma-ray sources are for example "[...] normal galaxies (including our own), active galactic nuclei, starburst galaxies, radio galaxies, pulsars, galactic black hole candidates, and supernova remnants" ([3] p.14). As the names suggest, starburst galaxies are galaxies with an extraordinarily high rate of star formation (cf. [3] p.93) and radio galaxies are defined by their intense emission of radiation in the radio-spectrum. While pulsars and supernova remnants are present in our own galaxy as well, the active galactic nuclei (AGN) are an example for extragalactic source types (cf. [6] p.1).

AGNs are the strikingly bright cores of active galaxies, which differ from "normal" galaxies in that their spectra go from Infrared up to Gamma-ray wavelengths and they also show strong variability (cf. [4] p.285f.). AGNs are assumed to be powered by supermassive BHs that accrete mass and release gravitational energy in the process (cf. [4] p.287). An example for AGNs are 'quasars' (quasistellar radio sources), which are "[...] the brightest objects in the universe" ([7] p. 8) that have a star-like appearance (hence the name) but are observed at high redshifts, corresponding to "[...] distances of billions of light-years" ([8] p.276). When these compact objects emit radio jets that are almost perfectly directed towards Earth, they are called Blazars (cf. [7] p.6).

Another extragalactic source candidate that stands out from the rest, since the energy content of these events are unparalleled (cf. [3] p. 230), are the Gamma-Ray Bursts (GRBs). Concerning what are the causes of GRBs, especially with respect to the ones of shorter duration, the details are not yet completely understood. While for long GRBs it is almost certain, that an explosion of a massive star, more precisely a Type Ic Supernova (SN), is involved (cf. [9] p.540f.), the favorite models for short GRBs are coalescences of a Black Hole and a Neutron Star, or of two Neutron Stars (cf. [9] p.542). A SN is the explosion of a star and both Neutron Stars and Black Holes are possible, very dense, remnants of a massive star collapsing, with the latter creating so much gravity, that even light can't escape their event horizon. Type Ic SN are Supernovae, whose spectra show no Hydrogen and Helium absorption lines (cf. [10] p.421). During the GRB's lifetime, which ranges from less than a second to a maximum of hundreds of seconds, they are brighter than any other gamma-ray source (cf. [9] p.1). The majority of the resulting photon energies is emitted in the domain of 100 keV to 1 MeV (cf. [9] p.9), but the upper limit even goes beyond 10 GeV (cf. [3] p.229).

Pulsars, as one of the mentioned galactic gamma-ray sources, are assumed to result from a SN leading to a Neutron Star (as shortly broached above, these are dense stars, whose collapsing progenitor had a mass greater than the sun (cf. [8] p.248)) that, while rotating, emit periodic radiation in the radio-frequency range (cf. [8] p.272). Both Pulsars and Blazars contribute to some of the brightest spots in Figure 1.2, which presents Fermi-LAT's 1-year all-sky view on gamma-rays in the Universe.

Figure 1.2: The Gamma-ray sky, as constructed through Fermi-LAT observations over one year. Credit: NASA/DOE/Fermi LAT Collaboration

Another event type happening also within our galaxy, so within the plane that is seen as a bright line in the center of the figure, are Novae. These are stars (mostly compact ones with a mass similar to that of the Sun, called 'White Dwarfs' (cf. [8] p.341)) that, by accreting mass from another star, send out long-lasting emissions (usually for months), that are well suited for observations due to their brightness, although they're not as bright as SN for example (cf. [8] p.253).

In the analysis sections 3.1 and 3.2 two examples for gamma-ray sources are used in a comparison with the telescopes' sensitivity curves. The first example is the just mentioned Nova, while the second one covers a blazar, to represent an extragalactic source.

1.1.4 Detection of Gamma-rays

Trying to detect gamma-rays directly would fail, for their wavelengths are too small to be reflected by mirrors and hence cannot be captured (cf. [11]). What comes pretty close to being called a 'direct' observation though, is how satellite-based gamma-ray instruments like Fermi-LAT work. Its gamma-ray detection method is based on the fact that photons, above the energy threshold of twice the electron rest mass, can produce an electron-positron pair when there is something present that can act as a reaction partner, to absorb some of the photon's momentum, usually in form of a nucleon. An example for this procedure is discussed in subsection 1.5 which goes into detail about Fermi-LAT's functionality.

But aside from that, ground-based observatories like HESS and CTAO are also able to detect gamma-rays in a more indirect way. That is because despite the fact that the Earth's atmosphere blocks most of these highly energetic photons through collisions and interactions with the atoms, it's very well possible to detect the secondary radiations that are the results from these processes. As the primary photon interactions lead to the production of plenty of pions, these decay into further particles. In the case of neutral pions this mostly leads to the production of two photons, which are able to do the above mentioned pair-production. The resulting electrons can emit additional gamma-rays through Bremsstrahlung (shortly elucidated in section 1.1.2), which causes an electromagnetic cascade by the repeated processes of e^+e^- productions and Bremsstrahlung (for the whole air shower procedure cf. [12]). When the electrons and positrons from these cascades exceed the local phase velocity of the light (c/n with n representing the refractive index), they emit Cherenkov radiation, which can then be observed by detectors on altitudes between sea- and mountain-level (cf. [5] p. 175f.), making it a relevant observation strategy. HESS and CTAO belong to the category of IACTs (Imaging Air Cherenkov Telescopes), because they make use of that phenomenon. But as a countermeasure to the lowness of the Cherenkov radiation intensity, large mirrors to collect and focus the light, as well as fast photomultipliers are needed (cf. [3] p.12). Also, as described in [3] p.12, to minimize the interference of all kinds of light sources, the observation of Cherenkov radiation has to be performed on nights having close to no light reflection from the moon. In contrast, when the energies of the gamma-rays get over 100 TeV, the induced electromagnetic showers in the atmosphere can reach sea-level, making it possible to observe these with large detectors (due to the small density of the electrons in question), independent of time and weather (cf. [5] p.182).

Of course other gamma-ray observation methods like the Compton telescopes, exploiting the Compton scattering processes (for a more detailed explanation read [2] p.269f.) are used, but for this thesis it's sufficient to focus on the procedures used by HESS, CTAO and Fermi-LAT.

1.1.5 Relevance of Gamma-ray Observation

Why is it of interest to look for gamma-rays? Aside from the possibility to put our knowledge of the physics of some of the underlying cosmic objects and events (like Black Holes, Super Novae (SN), Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN) as well as GRBs) to the test, gamma-ray observation also has several other benefits. Among other things, it allows for an insight into the element composition of planets, because chemical substances emit gamma-rays with very specific spectral lines when hit by cosmic rays, which can be for instance utilized as a check for hospitality towards human life (cf. [11]). Moreover the penetrating nature of gamma-rays enables an extraordinarily deep look into the history of the universe "[...] to the earliest epoch of the universe, possibly to $z \sim 100$ depending on the density of matter in the Universe" ([2] p.4), where z is the so called redshift which measures how strong observed wavelengths are stretched compared to when they were emitted, as a result of the expansion of the universe.

1.2 Sensitivity

In general terms the sensitivity S of a telescope is its capability to distinguish photons of a specific source from its background light. Aside from the intensity of the cosmic ray background, it is mostly dependent on the area A_{eff} of the primary lens, respectively of the combined collection area of the telescope arrays (like for HESS and CTAO), but also the observation time

t_{obs} and the quantum efficiency (Q.E.), which is the ratio between the photon-induced electrons that are detected and all the actual incoming photons. While S gets better for more A_{eff} and t_{obs} and a higher Q.E. enables observations at lower energy thresholds, background light is detrimental, which is the reason for choosing a small signal-to-noise ratio $\frac{N_\gamma}{N_{Bkg}}$. What is described here so far, is a definition of sensitivity as it is applied for instance in [13].

But beyond the just mentioned signal-to-noise ratio, there are more criteria that can be set, in order to specify what is called sensitivity. This leads to an alternative definition for S (like it is used in the section for sensitivity in [14] and also for this thesis) as the minimum photon-flux needed to fulfil those conditions. Other appropriate requirements for S are for example a minimum photon count $N_{\gamma,min}$ and a significance of a selected number of standard deviations σ . The significance s is a value that expresses how unlikely it is, that the observed data was obtained with the same number of on- and off-region counts, if it wasn't from a specific source, but from background light. This is explained more in-depth in the article by Li and Ma [15] which also includes the significance equation that is used in the codes: $s = \sqrt{-2\ln(\lambda)}$ (eq. 17 in [15] p.320) with λ being the ratio of maximum likelihood, which is the ratio of the probabilities that the detected number of on- and off-source photon counts are observed if the signal just comes randomly from some kind of background light or really from a specific photon source (cf. [15] p.319). What is described as on- and off-counts is the amount of observed photons that come from the region the telescope is pointed at (N_{on}), or from an area around the source (N_{off}). The used definition of significance by Li and Ma works best for more than 10 on- and off-region counts, but is also applicable to observations with fewer counts (cf. [15] p.323 f.).

For the so-called "integral sensitivity" these criteria only need to be fulfilled over a wide energy range, whereas for the "differential sensitivity", the energy is split into bins and for each of those the conditions have to be met. Therefore the evaluation of a telescope's differential sensitivity places higher demands on the photon source but on the other hand, if the differential sensitivity is exceeded by a detected flux, it is more reasonable to rule out the possibility that those photons are just background noise. This is also the reason why the tool is designed to calculate the sensitivity in the differential way. The inbuilt criteria are set to: $N_{\gamma,min} = 10$, $\frac{N_\gamma}{N_{Bkg}} = \frac{1}{20}$ and $s = 5\sigma$ (they can be changed to other values though), corresponding to a $5.733 \cdot 10^{-7}\%$ chance that if the signal was indeed just from background, it would have given at least the same amount of counts (the 5σ -value can be checked on [16]).

The actual sensitivity calculations of the tool are using so called Instrument Response Functions (IRFs), which provide information on the performance of each observatory. These performance values are based on Monte Carlo simulations and comprise i.a. the effective area and the acceptance of the detector, which represents the probabilities that a gamma-ray flux can be observed from a specific direction, implemented as the Point Spread Functions (PSFs) and with a certain energy, in form of the energy dispersion (cf. [1] and [17] p.3). Expanding on that, there are several particular parameters, that the code has to account for in the computation. When given an observation time, the spatial morphology (the tool is designed for point-like sources) and the spectral index of the gamma-ray source, first an energy migration matrix helps to turn the true energies into reconstructed energies, based on the shape of the source spectrum. Then the code uses the backgroundrate, observation time as well as the angular resolution to calculate the number of background counts N_{Bkg} , which divided by α , "the ratio of the acceptance-weighted exposure integrated in time and angular space over the signal and background region" ([18] p.1220), gives the off-region counts N_{off} . After that, the number of expected gamma-ray events N_γ from the source must fulfill all three above mentioned criteria,

when the simulated amount of gamma-rays from the assumed signal region added to N_{off} , gives the minimum value to meet these requirements, which is then giving the flux that defines the sensitivity.

For the procedure discussed here, see [19] p.24 f..

1.3 HESS

Figure 1.3: Complete telescope system of H.E.S.S. and H.E.S.S. II, Credit: H.E.S.S. collaboration, Clementina Medina

HESS (High Energy Stereoscopic System) is an array of IACTs, that can detect photons in the energy range between 10s of GeV and 10s of TeV. It consists of 5 telescopes, stationed in Namibia, from which the first 4 were constructed between 2002 and 2003, each having a mirror of 12 m diameter while the last telescope (called H.E.S.S. II), which was added in 2012, is 28 m in diameter. This allows for a peak effective area above 10^5m^2 . As explained in section 1.1.4, IACTs like HESS and CTAO observe the Cherenkov light, that is emitted by relativistic particles, created in an electromagnetic cascade that was initiated by gamma-ray collisions in the upper atmosphere and the photonic decays of the resulting pions. The illuminated ground area from the Cherenkov cone has a 250 m diameter on average, so the corresponding area of almost $50\,000\text{m}^2$ is covered by HESS' effective area. The telescopes' mirrors are focussed on a height of 10 km because the highly energetic air-showers, creating the Cherenkov radiation, mostly take place in that altitude. For a better analysis of the shower geometry the 4 smaller telescopes, which have a resolution of a couple of arcseconds, are placed in a square shape getting different angles on the Cherenkov radiation. The telescope cameras contain several photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) to improve the photon detection. They take images of the air showers that produced the Cherenkov light, to track the direction of the initial gamma-ray and the image intensity provides insight on the gamma-ray energy. HESS is sensitive to sources having a flux within some thousandths of the Crab Nebula flux, which is the sky's brightest steady gamma-ray emitting source.

All the info is taken from the official HESS website (cf. [20], [21]) and from the paper [22].

1.4 CTAO

Figure 1.4: Southern CTAO telescope array. Photo by Gabriel Pérez Diaz, IAC / Marc-André Besel, CTAO

The CTAO (Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory) is a group of IACTs as well, but it's a project that is still in the process of construction. Its main energy range for the observed photons will go from 20 GeV to a higher maximum of 300 TeV. It is a combination of two ground-based gamma-ray detector arrays that will stand out in terms of its sensitivity and accuracy in the High Energy domain with respect to its predecessors. The arrays are located in the northern and southern hemisphere and will contain more than 100 detectors in total. It is expected to reach 10 times the sensitivity and detection-rate of prior gamma-ray instruments i.a. due to its large collection area (its peak effective area will exceed 1km^2). In order to cover the above mentioned energy range, the telescopes are built in three different sizes, implemented as 70 small-, 40 medium- and 8 large-sized telescopes (SSTs, MSTs and LSTs). The installed primary reflectors have a diameter between 4.3 m and 23 m. While the SSTs are solely being installed on the southern hemisphere, near the Atacama Desert in Chile (because it provides an excellent view of our Galaxy's central region of many bright gamma-ray sources), the other two sizes are constructed on both sites, with the Northern location being on La Palma. For both arrays, at high energies (> 100 TeV) the angular resolution falls below 0.03° , while for the lower energy limits it goes up to 0.2° for the Southern and 0.25° for the Northern Array. As an IACT, CTAO works pretty similar to HESS. After the transient Cherenkov light (it only lasts for some billionths of a second) by the gamma-ray induced air showers gets reflected by mirrors it goes into PMTs and silicon Photomultipliers (SiPMs) to be turned into electric signals and get digitized, resulting in images of the shower.

The tool will make use of data, that's based on Monte Carlo Simulations assuming the first approved construction configuration for CTAO. It is called "Alpha Configuration" and consists of 4 LSTs and 9 MSTs on the Northern and 14 MSTs as well as 37 SSTs on the Southern site. This means that the sensitivities for CTAO, created in this thesis, only display the expected status of the first configuration, which includes a little more than half the amount of telescopes planned in total.

All the info was taken from the official CTAO website (cf. [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [14], [28], [29]).

1.5 Fermi-LAT

Figure 1.5: Image of Fermi-Satellite, Photo by Aurora Simonnet, NASA, Sonoma State University.

Fermi-LAT (Large Area Telescope) is the main observation instrument of the Fermi Gamma-ray Space Telescope (FGST). It is sensitive to gamma-rays that range from medium to Very High Energy (VHE), more precisely between 20 MeV and 300 GeV. With a 4x4 array of 40x40cm² towers it has a peak effective area above 8000 cm² and hence it covers 20% of the sky, which enables an all sky survey every 3 hours. Those towers are a combination of an anti-coincidence shield, conversion foils (thin metal sheets with a high proton number), 18 xy interleaved layers of silicon strip particle detectors and lastly a calorimeter (made of caesium iodide). This technology allows for a detection efficiency above 99% and a high signal-to-noise ratio. As for how exactly the detection works: gamma-rays are energetic enough to produce an electron-positron pair in the conversion foils, after which the electrons cause ionization in the silicon detectors so that the resulting electric pulses can be used for reconstructing the direction and finally the calorimeter measures the particle's energy. In the lower energy range the angular resolution is below 3.5°, while it gets to 0.15° for energies above 10 GeV. With the dead-time per event being below 100 μs it is low enough to consider the observation time being equal to the instrument's live-time. Its point source sensitivity above 100 MeV is better than $6 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for a one-year survey of the whole sky and a spectral index of 2.

All the info is taken from the websites of NASA and Stanford University (cf. [30], [31], [32], [33]).

2 Presentation of the Sensitivity Tool

2.1 Functionality and Dependencies

While it was outlined, in section 1.2, how sensitivity can be defined in general, the actual procedures for the code's sensitivity calculation are explained here. The created tool can be found on the following website: https://gitlab.desy.de/dario.mack/sensitivity-tool/-/blob/main/Sensitivity_Tool_v._1.0.ipynb

The sensitivity codes for CTAO, HESS and Fermi-LAT, which are based on a code ([34]) using `gammapy` ([35]) and another code ([36]) using `fermipy` ([37]), take a spectral index, the live-time (the time in which the observatory is used and is able to detect) as well as the three criteria $N_{\gamma,min}$, $\frac{N_{\gamma}}{N_{Bkg}}$ and significance s of the observations as input parameters, and output the differential sensitivity, for a point-like source, in form of tables and plots. It has two main features, that are showcased in the following sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2, which allow to either get the sensitivity vs energy for a specific live-time or show the time evolution of sensitivity for a fixed energy. It provides the option to do the calculations and plots either separately for each individual observatory or together in a combined plot. Beside the main inputs mentioned above, the codes have many in-built parameters (some of which were already explained in section 1.2), that contribute to the sensitivity computation.

To get more into detail, in the code used for HESS and CTAO first the field of view (FoV) and the angular offset of the FoV are specified. Then the energy range and the binning are set, for which the default values are adjusted to the energies that the observatories are sensitive to and each decade of energy is divided into 5 bins. This is followed by the IRFs. For CTAO, those are taken from [1] and are picked from the variants that are optimized for 0.5h, 5h and 50h of observation time (to choose the most appropriate one for each considered time) of the Southern site, which reaches better sensitivities compared to the Northern site, for a zenith angle of 20° , since bigger angles imply, that the incoming photons had to travel further and are therefore less likely to reach the detector. Due to that, the 20° zenith angle gives the best sensitivity (compared to the other options 40° and 60°), which is why the IRF used for HESS¹, is also optimized for a 20° zenith angle. It is also based on hybrid observation (all five telescopes), because that gives a better sensitivity in the energy range below 800 GeV (cf. [38] p.743). Finally, for Fermi-LAT sensitivity, the IRF P8R3_SOURCE_V3 for an isotropic emission model and the galactic interstellar emission model `gll_iem_v07.fits` in the `Fermitools` ([39]), on which the code is based on, are applied. Afterwards the live-time and the containment (the proportion of incoming photons, that we'd like to have inside the FoV between the angular cut-off) are defined. The angular cut θ is set to an average 0.05° for CTAO, in reference to the values for the angular resolution that can be found on the CTAO performance website [14]. Setting a containment for

¹The HESS IRF was kindly sent to me by R. D. Parsons from the HESS collaboration on request

HESS in the code is not needed, since its IRF has its data already cut to a θ value of 0.09° . Instead, for CTAO an energy-dependent containment of 80% is used, like in many papers (e.g. in [19] p.17). Regarding the live-time, it has to be stressed, that in contrast to Fermi-LAT which can observe quasi-continuously, CTAO and HESS are limited in their daily (or rather nightly) observation hours. As already touched upon in section 1.1.4, the light reflected by the moon interferes too much with the IACT detections, so they have to rely on the darkest phase of the night. For CTAO transient sources in the VHE energy regime are observed for around 5 hours per night on average (cf. [40] p. 188), which should be pretty alike to the situation for HESS. Consequently, for all the following plots, that compare the three observatories, different live-times are considered, so for example 5 hours for CTAO and HESS are compared with 1 day for Fermi-LAT. After that and the ensuing background estimation, the spectral model is adjusted with the respective index, assuming that the flux follows a power-law of the form: $\frac{dN}{dE} = \phi_0 \left(\frac{E}{E_0}\right)^{-\Gamma}$, where ϕ_0 is the flux amplitude, E and E_0 are the energy and reference energy and Γ refers to the spectral index. Another needed information is the value for α . CTAO uses a value of 0.2 by convention (c.f. [19] p.19), but that is also observation-dependent, which will be of importance in the specific gamma-ray source observations in section 3. Finally the set of criteria: $N_{\gamma,min}$, $\frac{N_\gamma}{N_{Bkg}}$ and the significance s are chosen, to calculate the sensitivity, which is then plotted in units of $\frac{erg}{cm^2.s}$ against the energy in units of TeV on a logarithmic scale for both axes. It was expounded in section 1.2 that the significance calculation of the code works on the basis of an equation by Li and Ma ([15]) that uses a maximum likelihood method. For both the `fermipy` and `gammapy` code, this is evident from the explanations on the respective websites (cf. [36] and [34]). From here on, two specific sets of criteria are used as 'strict' and 'loose' criteria:

criteria	strict	loose
$N_{\gamma,min}$	10	5
significance	5	2
$\frac{N_\gamma}{N_{Bkg}}$	0.05	0.1

Table 2.1: 'Strict' and 'loose' sets of sensitivity criteria, used in this thesis.

Other than the observation time, the spectral index, the energy range as well as the: $N_{\gamma,min}$ and TS threshold (which is the significance squared) criteria, the code for Fermi-LAT sensitivity also takes inputs like the galactic coordinates, to specify the source origin. Per default, these coordinates are set to a longitude of 120° and a latitude of 45° (the North Celestial pole), like in [41], because giving the FoV an offset from the Galactic center, that is disturbed by a lot of background light, gives a better sensitivity.

Additional to the mentioned `gammapy` and `fermipy`, the code utilizes the following packages: `regions` ([42]), `numpy` ([43]), `matplotlib` ([44]), `pandas` ([45]) and `astropy` ([46]) and it was programmed with `python` ([47]) as a `jupyter notebook` ([48]).

²Info taken from R. D. Parsons of the HESS Collaboration

2.2 Sensitivity Comparisons

2.2.1 Sensitivity vs Energy

First we can visualise the sensitivity of the three gamma-ray instruments HESS, CTAO and Fermi-LAT versus energy, for a specific observation time. Since the tool gives the possibility to not only show the single observatory sensitivities, but also the comparison of all three, and due to the energy ranges and sensitivities being so different for Fermi-LAT compared to HESS and CTAO, it makes more sense to show the combined plot, which is given by Figure 2.1. It shows the sensitivities for an exemplary spectral index of 2.62, the 'strict' set of criteria from Table 2.1 and live-times of 5h (left) and 25h (right) for CTAO and HESS, respectively for 1 and 5 days for Fermi-LAT. The reason for choosing different live-times for the IACTs and Fermi-LAT was discussed in section 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Comparison of the sensitivities of HESS, CTAO and Fermi-LAT, for a spectral index of 2.62, strict criteria: significance= 5σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 10$, signal-to-background-ratio=0.05 and a live-time of 5h (left) and 25h (right) for CTAO and HESS resp. 1 day (left) and 5 days (right) for Fermi-LAT

Focussing on the comparison between the three observatories first, there are some obvious differences. Regarding the best sensitivities achieved by each instrument on the considered timescales, Fermi-LAT isn't able to match those of the two IACTs. It is surpassed, by a factor of more than 50 in the case of HESS and by two orders of magnitude by CTAO, with CTAO's sensitivity being more than 3 times better than that of HESS. Nevertheless, bearing in mind the fact that Fermi-LAT isn't timely restricted in its observations, as opposed to the IACTs, the sensitivities will typically get way better than for the 1 and 5 days shown here. Aside from that, it should be highlighted that the energy scales, at which the two different types of gamma-ray instruments are the most sensitive, are very distinct. For Fermi-LAT that is the domain of 100s of MeV, while HESS and CTAO work best in the TeV regime. Using both kinds of gamma-ray observatories is therefore pretty valuable, since it allows for a wider coverage of the energy scale.

By comparing shorter with longer live-times, it is apparent how much better the sensitivities can get, when extending the duration of observation. In the second plot of the figure, the live-time used is five times longer than for the first plot. The result is a sensitivity more than twice the one for shorter observation. Although this shows the beneficial effect pretty clearly,

it is always dependent on the gamma-ray source how reasonable certain observation times are, because many events are only shortly observable. How exactly the sensitivity evolves with increasing live-time is shown in section 2.2.2.

To specifically see, where in the energy range of a sensitivity curve what criterion typically is the defining limiting factor of the sensitivity, Figure 2.2 was generated. It illustrates the sensitivity curve for CTAO with 'loose' criteria, a spectral index of 2.62 and a live-time of 5 hours.

Figure 2.2: Sensitivity of CTAO with a spectral index of 2.62 and a live-time of 5h for looser criteria: $\text{significance}=2\sigma$, $N_{\gamma,\text{min}} = 5$, $\text{signal-to-background-ratio}=0.1$ (right).

As can be seen by the differently coloured lines in the plot, the defining criterion at the lower end of the energy range is signal-background-ratio. This can be explained by the fact, that background light dominates the lower energy segment. In the central energy region, where the observatories have their highest sensitivities, the amount of observed gamma-rays is so high and the background light can be rejected so reliably, that the significance is the remaining criterion to decide over the sensitivity. At the upper end of the considered energy range, the minimum gamma-ray count becomes the prevalent criterion, because there are fewer and fewer gamma-rays that are able too reach these energies.

2.2.2 Sensitivity vs Observation Time

To demonstrate the second feature of the code, Figure 2.3 displays the sensitivities versus live-time of the observatories, again for a spectral index of 2.62, and the 'strict' set of criteria. The amount of observed gamma-rays is proportional to the live-time and since two of the criteria that define the sensitivity ($N_{\gamma,min}$ and $\frac{N_{\gamma}}{N_{Bkg}}$, as explained in section 1.2) are linearly dependent on the number of gamma-rays, the minimum flux that fulfils these conditions gets lower (also on a linear scale). This means, that the sensitivity gets better and it is also the reason for why it doesn't matter which range of hours are compared to show the time dependency. For the comparison of the sensitivity evolutions it has to be taken into account, that Fermi-LAT will typically get far greater observation times on the gamma-ray sources, so that the sensitivity can get way better than the ones shown in the Figure 2.3. It shows the sensitivities between live-times of a quarter-hour and 50 hours at the same energy (100 GeV) for all three observatories.

Figure 2.3: Comparison of the sensitivities of HESS, CTAO and Fermi-LAT versus live-time at 100 GeV, for a spectral index of 2.62 and strict criteria: significance= 5σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 10$, signal-to-background-ratio=0.05, in quarter-hour steps up to 50h.

100 GeV is an energy that all three instruments are sensitive to. However, for Fermi-LAT it is not too far away from its upper energy limit at around 300 GeV. Thus, its calculated sensitivities in the figure are a lot worse than what Fermi-LAT is capable of (for HESS and

CTAO that applies as well, but to a smaller degree). Adding to the mentioned fact, that Fermi-LAT observes longer in general, the sensitivity for Fermi-LAT is hard to compare with the two IACTs. For the chosen energy, the figure shows that HESS and CTAO are between 3 and 5 orders of magnitude more sensitive than Fermi-LAT. More importantly though, the linear improvement in sensitivity is demonstrated and the chosen range of live-times gives a good insight into the sensitivities for an array of different observation durations.

2.2.3 Sensitivity for different Criteria

As the criteria for the sensitivity calculation can be set differently, depending on how reliably the data is intended to come from the observed gamma-ray source, it's interesting to see, how much the sensitivity depends on these criteria. For the presentations of observatories' performances, like here [14] for CTAO, the used criteria: $N_{\gamma,min} = 10$, $\frac{N_{\gamma}}{N_{Bkg}} = \frac{1}{20}$ and $s = 5\sigma$, are arguably quite strict. Because not only does a significance of e.g. 2σ still have a low chance of 4.55% to result from background light (2σ -value from [49]), it also needs to be considered, that in many observations, less than 10 counts will be detected in some energy bins which could be meaningful nevertheless. That is why viewing additional sensitivity curves for the 'looser' set of criteria (from Table 2.1) is also reasonable, since it may give a more realistic impression, of whether a flux is actually detectable by the observatories. Hence, Figure 2.4 was created to see the difference between the sensitivities for strict and looser criteria. By comparing the data at the points of best sensitivity, it is apparent that it is improved by a factor between 2 and 3 for the less restrictive conditions, illustrating the impact of the set criteria. The applied parameters for this example are a spectral index of 2.62 and a live-time of 5h for HESS and CTAO, respectively 1d for Fermi-LAT.

Figure 2.4: Sensitivity comparison of HESS, CTAO and Fermi-LAT, for a spectral index of 2.62, a live-time of 5h for HESS and CTAO, resp. 1 day for Fermi-LAT for strict criteria: significance= 5σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 10$, signal-to-background-ratio=0.05 (left) and looser criteria: significance= 2σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 5$, signal-to-background-ratio=0.1 (right).

Moreover, there is another crucial element of the sensitivity calculation, which is the defined amount of bins per energy decade, in which the requirements have to be fulfilled. When the number of bins is reduced, the sensitivity strongly benefits, because if the bin-size grows, there is a wider energy range for flux to be detected and so meeting the criteria like a minimum gamma-ray count becomes a lot easier. To see the impact of changing the amount of bins, two plots (seen in Figure 2.5) showing the sensitivity of CTAO were created. The first shows the default calculation with 5 bins per decade of energy, while for the second one each decade comprises only 2 bins.

Figure 2.5: Sensitivity of CTAO, with a spectral index of 2.62, a live-time of 5h, strict criteria: significance= 5σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 10$ and signal-to-background-ratio=0.05, for 5 bins (left) and 2 bins (right) per energy decade.

In the points of best sensitivity, the 2-bin calculation shows a sensitivity that's improved by around 50%, compared to the 5-bin alternative. This reinforces again how much of an effect the defined criteria have on the computed sensitivity. So, adding to $N_{\gamma,min}$, significance and the signal-to-background ratio, changing the bin-size per energy decade is one more option, to see how the requirements on the gamma-ray source limit the possible detection thresholds.

3 Sensitivity Analysis for specific Source Types

With the sensitivity tool it is now possible to look at specific types of gamma-ray sources, and compare their observed flux with the sensitivity curves of the observatories at their respective energy regimes. This can give a feeling for how well the three instruments are able to resolve such kind of events. However, as addressed in the last section 2.3, it isn't possible to have full clarity over the observability, by just looking at the sensitivity. Due to the strongly different outputs, depending on how strict the criteria are set (which was displayed in Figure 2.4), that don't necessarily have to be fulfilled for real observations, it has to be kept in mind that even flux points below the calculated sensitivity may be detected and are not inevitably from background noise. Thus, for each of the following observations, one sensitivity curve for strict and one for looser criteria (see Table 2.1) are presented, to see how far the detected flux lies from both versions. With the chosen examples depicting real observations, the comparison can also give hints at limits of the sensitivity calculation. The two following sections cover a galactic and an extragalactic source type.

3.1 RS Ophiuchi

For an example of a galactic gamma-ray source we look at the Nova RS Ophiuchi. The data used is taken from the Auxiliary information given on [50], which is based on the HESS Collaboration's article [51] and includes i.a. the Fermi-LAT data, the HESS data and also a code to create the spectral curve, for five nights of observation starting on August 9th 2021, from which the fifth night data is used in Figure 3.1, together with the corresponding sensitivity curves for both the stricter and looser criteria.

According to the paper, RS Ophiuchi is a recurrent Nova consisting of a white dwarf, moving around a red giant star, accreting mass in the process and sending out explosive shocks of radiation as a result (cf. [51] p.13 f.), which fits the definition of Novae, as described in section 1.1.3. It is located at a distance of 1.4 kpc to Earth (cf. [51] p.30) and its location is given by a right ascension of $17^h 50^{min} 13.6^s$ and declination of $-06^\circ 42' 28.5''$ (cf. [51] p. 5). These coordinates were converted into galactic coordinates (using [52]) and rounded to: $l=19.8^\circ$, $b=10.37^\circ$ as an input for the code. Likewise, every other parameter of the sensitivity calculation was adjusted to match the given data as well as possible. While for Fermi-LAT a whole day of observation time was assumed, the 2.8h live-time of HESS was taken from the paper (cf. [51] p.6). The spectral index for HESS was set to 3.24, whereas for Fermi-LAT an index of 2.05 was used, based on [51] p.9, 12. Since there was no specification for α , a typical value of 0.2 was used for CTAO and HESS, as explained in section 2.1. Live-time and spectral index for the CTAO sensitivity were set identical to HESS. Furthermore, the energy bins for the generated plots were matched to the data. Additional to the packages, that are used in the sensitivity tool

(mentioned in section 2.1), the code provided on the website [50] utilizes the `naima` package ([53]).

Figure 3.1: Sensitivity comparison of CTAO, HESS and Fermi-LAT for the observation of Nova RS Ophiuchi, with a live-time of 2.8h and a spectral index of 3.24 for CTAO and HESS, resp. an observation time of 1 day and a spectral index of 2.05 for Fermi-LAT for strict criteria: significance= 5σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 10$, signal-to-background-ratio=0.05 (left) and looser criteria: significance= 2σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 5$, signal-to-background-ratio=0.1 (right).

Looking at the two plots, it becomes clear once again, how much of a difference the definition of sensitivity can make. While the sensitivity curves for stricter criteria mostly lie above the Nova fluxpoints, the sensitivity for looser criteria are clearly better at showing the actual observability of the Nova because the majority of points exceed the sensitivity. As opposed to this, the sensitivity curve of CTAO implies, that it would be able to observe the flux even when setting stronger requirements, since it's smaller than the fluxpoints for both conditions. Another important point, stressed with the plots, is that (as touched upon in section 2.2.1) both kinds of detectors are valuable for the observation, because among the three considered observatories, in the spectrum of the GeV-regime or below, only Fermi-LAT is sensitive enough for the considered flux points and on the other hand, in the TeV-regime the sensitivity of the two IACTs are better by several orders of magnitude and are thus much more likely to observe the Nova flux at those energies.

If we wanted to look at a comparable event at around 3 times the distance of RS Ophiuchi, what would that look like, with respect to the sensitivities? Such an event would be approximately 4.2kpc away and is therefore still on a galactic scale, having in mind that this would be just above half the distance to the Milky Way center, for which [54] (without the errors) states a value of 8.178kpc. Concluding from the inverse-square law, the energy flux would be smaller by a factor of $3^2 = 9$, which can be approximated (because we just want to make a rough example) by lowering all the datapoints by one order of magnitude. Such an event is visualised in Figure 3.2, using all the same plotting parameters as for the Nova.

Figure 3.2: Sensitivity comparison of CTAO, Fermi-LAT and HESS for a Nova-like object for a distance of about 4.2kpc, with an observation time of 2.8h and a spectral index of 3.24 for CTAO and HESS and an observation time of 1d and a spectral index of 2.05 for Fermi-LAT for strict criteria: significance= 5σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 10$, signal-to-background-ratio=0.05 (left) and looser criteria: significance= 2σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 5$, signal-to-background-ratio=0.1 (right).

What's immediately evident from these plots is that an event like this would be much harder to detect by the three observatories, than a Nova at the distance of RS Ophiuchi. The strict criteria make it seem like there might be no chance for an observation, judging from the fact that even the closest flux points are less than half of the respective sensitivity values. However the sensitivities for looser criteria are a lot closer to the flux points, retaining the possibility of detection, at least for Fermi-LAT and CTAO, also considering that even the defined loose conditions have a chance of being too restrictive, when looking at real observations, that fulfil one or two of the criteria but not all three.

Figure 3.3: Sensitivity comparison of HESS, CTAO and Fermi-LAT for a Nova-like object for a distance of about 4.2kpc, for loose criteria: significance= 2σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 5$, signal-to-background-ratio=0.1, a spectral index of 3.24 for CTAO and HESS, resp. 2.05 for Fermi-LAT, and a live-time of 5h for HESS and CTAO, resp. 1 day for Fermi-LAT.

If we had the chance to observe this event for a little longer though, the situation would be a little different, as shown in Figure 3.3. It presents the sensitivities for 'loose' criteria for a live-time of 5h for HESS and CTAO, respectively 1 day for Fermi-LAT.

5 hours of observation time for a Nova isn't too unrealistic, judging from the fact that the emissions from a Nova can last for months (see section 1.1.3). So, with some of the flux points almost overlapping with CTAO's sensitivity curve, it looks even more promising to observe such an event. Also keeping in mind that the sensitivity for CTAO still assumes the "Alpha Configuration", which has less telescopes than planned for the complete CTAO, this gives even more hope for further gamma-ray detections, like the one discussed here.

3.2 PKS 0736+01

For an extragalactic gamma-ray source we'll look at the blazar PKS 0736+01, also named PKS 0736+017, which has a distance of (840.75 ± 58.85) Mpc, as stated on the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database [55]. The data used is taken from the HESS observations [56] of the blazar on four days in February 2015, focussing on the 19th, which was the night of the dominating signal. The datafiles¹ for HESS and Fermi-LAT provided the butterflies seen in Figure 3.3 but also more details of the observational parameters. For the HESS data a Power-Law model of the type shown in section 2.1 was fitted with the amplitude $\phi_0 = 1.13576 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{TeV}^{-1}$, the spectral index $\Gamma = 4.20118$ and reference energy $E_0 = 0.2 \text{TeV}$. The value for the index was then used for the sensitivity curves for CTAO and HESS, as well as a live-time of 1.73h and an α of 0.05, also taken from the HESS data files. Again the energy bins were chosen to match the data. For the Fermi-LAT sensitivity the spectral index of 2.15 was taken from the paper (cf. [56] p.5) and an observation time of one day was assumed.

Figure 3.4: Sensitivity comparison of HESS, CTAO and Fermi-LAT for the blazar PKS0736+01, with a live-time of 1.73h and a spectral index of 4.20118 for HESS and CTAO, resp. an observation time of 1 day and a spectral index of 2.15 for Fermi-LAT for strict criteria: significance= 5σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 10$, signal-to-background-ratio=0.05 (left) and looser criteria: significance= 2σ , $N_{\gamma,min} = 5$, signal-to-background-ratio=0.1 (right).

¹The HESS collaboration kindly granted me access to the files for that night of observation from HESS and Fermi-LAT.

Figure 3.3 shows not only the already discussed importance of the defined requirements for the calculated sensitivity, but it also emphasizes the fact, that an observation can go way below the instrument's assigned sensitivity. Making assumptions on the observability of specific gamma-ray sources, on the basis of the sensitivities computed by this tool, should be done very carefully. Even though the gamma-rays from the blazar were detected over a wide energy range, both fluxes for Fermi-LAT and HESS are only partly above the sensitivity curves, when looking at the 'loose' conditions. With 'strict' conditions, the plot makes it seem like HESS, different to CTAO and Fermi-LAT, wouldn't have been able to detect any flux at all.

4 Conclusion

This code was created to provide data on the differential sensitivities of multi-wavelength-instruments, more precisely in the gamma-ray spectrum, for use in the field of astroparticle-physics and especially for time-domain studies in that field.

It is based on codes from `gammapy` [34] and `fermipy` [36] and is able to calculate and plot the point-source sensitivities of the three observatories HESS, CTAO and Fermi-LAT either for a fixed observation time vs energy or vice versa. It also takes the minimum gamma-ray count $N_{\gamma,min}$, significance s and the signal-to-background ratio $\frac{N_{\gamma}}{N_{Bkg}}$ as input parameters, because they have a strong impact on the computed sensitivities. The respective energy regimes for which the code is designed, are guided by the boundaries of each instrument (20 GeV-300 TeV for CTAO, 10s of GeV-10s of TeV for HESS and 20 MeV-300 GeV for Fermi-LAT). For the sensitivity vs time plots, a timespan of 50 hours in quarter-hour steps is used, which should be sufficient to most observations and shows how the sensitivity improves with time. There are options to get the individual plots for each instrument or to display them together in one plot for a comparison.

In the analysis the code was able to show how the sensitivities of the observatories compare not only to each other, but also to the fluxes of some observed (or theoretical in the case of the second example in section 3.1) gamma-ray source types of galactic (Nova Rs Ophiuchi) and extragalactic origin (blazar PKS0736+01). Figure 2.1 illustrates that HESS and CTAO are between 1 and 2 orders of magnitude more sensitive than Fermi-LAT, while focussing on a higher energy regime. Furthermore, as the plots were generated for two different sets of criteria: $N_{\gamma,min} = 10$, $\frac{N_{\gamma}}{N_{Bkg}} = \frac{1}{20}$ and $s = 5\sigma$ for stricter and $N_{\gamma,min} = 5$, $\frac{N_{\gamma}}{N_{Bkg}} = \frac{1}{10}$ and $s = 2\sigma$ for looser conditions), it is apparent, how strong the sensitivity calculation is dependent on the definition of these criteria (Figure 2.4 gave a 2-3 times better sensitivity for looser criteria), which is useful to keep in mind, when interpreting sensitivities with respect to actual flux observability for the respective instruments. As the looser set of criteria e.g. bears a greater risk of signal-background-misinterpretation, it is better at illustrating what flux may be detected in real observations. But even with looser criteria, some detected events like the blazar PKS0736+01 revealed in the comparison with the observatories' sensitivities, that the latter aren't able to fully display the source's observability.

Additional to the three mentioned requirements, the set amount of bins per decade of energy, in which these criteria have to be fulfilled, was also demonstrated to have a great impact on the sensitivity calculation. A change from 5 to 2 bins per decade gave an improved sensitivity by about 50%.

To further widen the usability of the code, sensitivity calculations for further instruments could be included. Some examples that come to mind are MAGIC (Major Atmospheric Gamma Imaging Cherenkov Telescope), VERITAS (Very Energetic Radiation Imaging Telescope Array

System) and HAWC (High-Altitude Water Cherenkov Observatory).

A minor additional part of the code for HESS and CTAO allows for an analysis of what criterion was the hardest to fulfil for each energy, to see what limits the sensitivity the most at that energy. This feature could be added to the code for Fermi-LAT as well in the future.

Also, since the code is based on `fermipy` and `gammapy`, it could be edited to work with the newest versions of the modules. While the `fermipy` code is using the most current `Fermitools` version, the `gammapy` version 0.18.2, for which the code was developed, can already be updated to version 0.20.1 but when using the code within one kernel, the `gammapy` version needs to work in the Fermi environment which wasn't the case for the follow-up versions of 0.18.2.

As can be seen in the plots for HESS, the region of best sensitivity is not as smooth, as for the other two instruments, which is probably due to the IRF. So using other IRFs may improve that.

Making the angular cut dependent on the energy for HESS, like it's done for CTAO, could be another possible way to get higher precision of the tool's sensitivity calculation.

And lastly, the code is build to calculate the differential sensitivity, so for situations where also the integral sensitivity is of interest, the code could be improved to include that option as well. Just changing the amount of bins to 1 doesn't give the correct integral sensitivity, because while the code for Fermi-LAT includes the option to pick the 'eflux' values instead of the 'e2dnde', the sensitivity calculations for HESS and CTAO don't include the former option, which would indeed integrate the energy with the differential flux, whereas the latter just multiplies the differential flux with the square of the reference energy.

Bibliography

- [1] Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory and Cherenkov Telescope Array Consortium. *CTAO Instrument Response Functions - prod5 version v0.1*. Version v0.1. Zenodo, Sept. 2021. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5499840. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5499840>.
- [2] E. L. Chupp. *Gamma-Ray Astronomy Nuclear Transition Region*. eng. 1st ed. 1976. Geophysics and Astrophysics Monographs ; 14. Dordrecht, 1976. ISBN: 9789401014960.
- [3] K. S. Cheng and Gustavo E. Romero. *Cosmic Gamma-Ray Sources*. eng. Vol. 304. Astrophysics and Space Science Library. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 2004. ISBN: 9789048166251.
- [4] Volker Schönfelder and M Harwit. *The Universe in Gamma Rays*. eng. Astronomy and Astrophysics Library. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin / Heidelberg, 2001. ISBN: 3642087450.
- [5] P. V. Ramana Murthy and A. W. Wolfendale. *Gamma-ray Astronomy*. 2nd ed. Cambridge Astrophysics. Cambridge University Press, 1993. DOI: 10.1017/CB09780511564840.
- [6] Yang Chen et al. "Chapter 2 Galactic Gamma-ray Sources". In: *Chinese Physics C* 46.3 (Mar. 2022), p. 030002. DOI: 10.1088/1674-1137/ac3fa8. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1674-1137/ac3fa8>.
- [7] Françoise Combes. *Active Galactic Nuclei*. 2514-3433. IOP Publishing, 2021. ISBN: 978-0-7503-3035-0. DOI: 10.1088/2514-3433/ac2a27. URL: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/2514-3433/ac2a27>.
- [8] Kenneth R Lang. *A Companion to Astronomy and Astrophysics Chronology and Glossary with Data Tables*. eng. New York, NY, 2006. ISBN: 9780387333670.
- [9] Gilbert Vedrenne and Jean-Luc Atteia. *Gamma-Ray Bursts: The Brightest Explosions in the Universe*. eng. Springer Praxis Books. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin / Heidelberg, 2009. ISBN: 9783540390855.
- [10] Bing Zhang. *The physics of gamma-ray bursts*. eng. Cambridge, 2019. ISBN: 9781139226530 ebook.
- [11] Science Mission Directorate. "Gamma Rays" NASA Science. 2010. National Aeronautics and Space Administration. URL: https://science.nasa.gov/ems/12_gammarays. access date: 2022-08-18.
- [12] Peter Dunne. *Demonstrating cosmic ray induced electromagnetic cascades*. Preston College, Preston, Lancashire, UK. From the CERN and High School Teachers Programme at CERN. URL: <https://hst-archive.web.cern.ch/archiv/hst2000/teaching/expt/muons/cascades.htm>. access date: 2022-09-03.
- [13] Richard McCray. JILA. URL: https://jila.colorado.edu/~ajsh/courses/astr1120_03/text/chapter2/L2S3.htm, access date: 2022-08-24.

- [14] Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory gGmbH. URL: <https://www.cta-observatory.org/science/ctao-performance/>. access date: 2022-08-22.
- [15] T.-P. Li and Y. Ma. “Analysis methods for results in gamma-ray astronomy”. In: *The Astrophysical Journal* 272 (Aug. 1983), pp. 317–324. DOI: 10.1086/161295.
- [16] Wolfram | Alpha. URL: <https://www.wolframalpha.com/input?i=5+sigma>, access date: 2022-08-17.
- [17] M. Ackermann et al. “THE FERMI LARGE AREA TELESCOPE ON ORBIT: EVENT CLASSIFICATION, INSTRUMENT RESPONSE FUNCTIONS, AND CALIBRATION”. In: *ApJS* 203:4 (2012). DOI: 10.1088/0067-0049/203/1/4.
- [18] Berge, D., Funk, S., and Hinton, J. “Background modelling in very-high-energy γ -ray astronomy”. In: *A&A* 466.3 (2007), pp. 1219–1229. DOI: 10.1051/0004-6361:20066674. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20066674>.
- [19] K. Bernlöhner et al. “Monte Carlo design studies for the Cherenkov Telescope Array”. In: *Astroparticle Physics* 43 (Mar. 2013), pp. 171–188. DOI: 10.1016/j.astropartphys.2012.10.002.
- [20] H.E.S.S. collaboration. URL: <https://www.mpi-hd.mpg.de/hfm/HESS/pages/about/>. access date: 2022-08-21.
- [21] W. Hofmann. H.E.S.S. collaboration. 2012, URL: <https://www.mpi-hd.mpg.de/hfm/HESS/pages/about/telescopes/>. access date: 2022-08-21.
- [22] Wstan Benbow and HESS Collaboration. “The status and performance of HESS”. In: *AIP Conference Proceedings*. Vol. 745. 1. American Institute of Physics. 2005, pp. 611–616. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1878471>.
- [23] Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory gGmbH. URL: <https://www.cta-observatory.org/about/>. access date: 2022-08-21.
- [24] Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory gGmbH. URL: <https://www.cta-observatory.org/project/technology/>. access date: 2022-08-21.
- [25] Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory gGmbH. URL: <https://www.cta-observatory.org/about/how-cta-works/>. access date: 2022-08-21.
- [26] Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory gGmbH. URL: <https://www.cta-observatory.org/about/array-locations/la-palma/>. access date: 2022-08-21.
- [27] Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory gGmbH. URL: <https://www.cta-observatory.org/about/array-locations/chile/>. access date: 2022-08-21.
- [28] Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory gGmbH. URL: <https://www.cta-observatory.org/project/technology/sst/>. access date: 2022-08-21.
- [29] Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory gGmbH. URL: <https://www.cta-observatory.org/project/technology/1st/>. access date: 2022-08-21.
- [30] National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Curator: J.D. Myers. NASA Official: Phil Newman. Science Official: Elizabeth Hays. 2011, URL: <https://fermi.gsfc.nasa.gov/science/instruments/lat.html>. access date: 2022-08-22.
- [31] National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Curator: J.D. Myers. NASA Official: Phil Newman. Science Official: Elizabeth Hays. 2011, URL: <https://fermi.gsfc.nasa.gov/science/instruments/table1-1.html>. access date: 2022-08-22.

- [32] Giovanna Senatore. Stanford University. URL: <https://glast.sites.stanford.edu/about#funding>. access date: 2022-08-22.
- [33] National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Page Editor: Rob Garner. NASA Official: Brian Dunbar. 2020, URL: <https://www.nasa.gov/content/goddard/fermi-spacecraft-and-instruments>. access date: 2022-08-22.
- [34] The Gammapy developers. URL: https://docs.gammapy.org/0.18.2/tutorials/cta_sensitivity.html, access date: 2022-08-18.
- [35] C. Deil et al. *Gammapy - A prototype for the CTA science tools*. Version 0.18.2. Jan. 2017. arXiv: 1709.01751 [astro-ph.IM].
- [36] Fermipy Developers Revision 36c6e9db. URL: <https://fermipy.readthedocs.io/en/latest/advanced/sensitivity.html>, access date: 2022-08-18.
- [37] M. Wood et al. *Fermipy: An open-source Python package for analysis of Fermi-LAT Data*. Version 1.1.3. Jan. 2017. arXiv: 1707.09551 [astro-ph.IM].
- [38] Y. Becherini, M. Punch, and H.E.S.S. Collaboration. “Performance of HESS-II in multi-telescope mode with a multi-variate analysis”. In: *AIP Conference Proceedings* 1505.1 (2012), pp. 741–744. DOI: 10.1063/1.4772366. eprint: <https://aip.scitation.org/doi/pdf/10.1063/1.4772366>. URL: <https://aip.scitation.org/doi/abs/10.1063/1.4772366>.
- [39] Fermi Science Support Development Team. *Fermitools: Fermi Science Tools*. Astrophysics Source Code Library, record ascl:1905.011. Version 2.2.0. May 2019. ascl: 1905.011.
- [40] The Ctao Consortium. *Science With The Cherenkov Telescope Array*. eng. Singapore: World Scientific Publishing Company, 2018. ISBN: 9789813270084.
- [41] Publically available data for Fermi LAT Performance created by Fermi-LAT collaboration. Page Editors: Simone Maldera, Matthew Wood, Regina Caputo, Riccardo Rando, Eric Charles, Seth Digel and Luca Baldini. Updated on Dec 01, 2021, URL: https://www.slac.stanford.edu/exp/glast/groups/canda/lat_Performance.htm. access date: 2022-09-04.
- [42] Larry Bradley et al. *astropy/regions: v0.5*. Version 0.5. Jan. 2022. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5826359. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5826359>.
- [43] Charles R. Harris et al. *Array programming with NumPy*. Version 1.21.6. Sept. 2020. DOI: 10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2>.
- [44] J. D. Hunter. *Matplotlib: A 2D graphics environment*. Version 3.2.2. 2007. DOI: 10.1109/MCSE.2007.55.
- [45] The pandas development team. *pandas-dev/pandas: Pandas*. Version 1.3.5. Feb. 2020. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3509134. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3509134>.
- [46] The Astropy Collaboration et al. *The Astropy Project: Building an Open-science Project and Status of the v2.0 Core Package*. Version 4.3.1. Sept. 2018. DOI: 10.3847/1538-3881/aabc4f. arXiv: 1801.02634 [astro-ph.IM].
- [47] Python Software Foundation. Version 3.7.12. Software available on URL: <https://www.python.org/>.
- [48] Thomas Kluyver et al. *Jupyter Notebooks – a publishing format for reproducible computational workflows*. Ed. by F. Loizides and B. Schmidt. Version 6.4.12. IOS Press, 2016.

- [49] Wolfram | Alpha. URL: <https://www.wolframalpha.com/input?i=2+sigma>, access date: 2022-08-17.
- [50] H.E.S.S. Collaboration. URL: https://www.mpi-hd.mpg.de/hfm/HESS/pages/publications/auxiliary/2022_RS_Oph/, access date: 2022-08-18.
- [51] F. Aharonian et al. “Time-resolved hadronic particle acceleration in the recurrent nova RS Ophiuchi”. In: *Science* 376.6588 (2022), pp. 77–80. DOI: 10.1126/science.abn0567. eprint: <https://www.science.org/doi/pdf/10.1126/science.abn0567>. URL: <https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.abn0567>.
- [52] NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database. Funded by National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Operated by California Institute of Technology. URL: https://ned.ipac.caltech.edu/coordinate_calculator. access date: 2022-08-28.
- [53] V. Zabalza. *naima: a Python package for inference of relativistic particle energy distributions from observed nonthermal spectra*. Version 0.10.0. 2015. eprint: 1509.03319.
- [54] P.A. Zyla et al. “Review of Particle Physics”. In: *PTEP* 2020.8 (2020), p. 083C01. DOI: 10.1093/ptep/ptaa104.
- [55] NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database. Funded by National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Operated by California Institute of Technology. URL: <https://ned.ipac.caltech.edu/uri/NED::ByName/PKS%200736%2b01>. access date: 2022-08-29.
- [56] H.E.S.S. Collaboration et al. “H.E.S.S. detection of very high-energy emission from the quasar PKS 0736+017”. In: *A&A* 633 (2020), A162. DOI: 10.1051/0004-6361/201935906. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201935906>.